

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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1 Summary

This Deliverable report (D3.1) has been prepared in the context of Work Package 3 (WP3) and Task 3.1.: “Novel screening platform technologies” of the OXIPRO project.

One of the aims of this task is to develop a biosensor array to monitor enzymatic activity through microfluidics. In this report we present results related to the development of the microfluidic screening platform ready for enzyme tests.

Another main aim of research reported in this report relates to the development of an efficient protocol for screening enzyme activities in which cell-free expression is used. In summary, the developed protocol could be used to confirm activity of novel flavoprotein oxidases within 48 hours after the arrival of the synthetic genes. The screening is suitable for a 96-well plate format thus providing a timesaving tool for the OXIPRO consortium for screening new (oxidative) enzymes.

As the above-mentioned two aims are distinct, the report is organized in two parts. The first part covers the work performed on the *microfluidics-based screening*, while the second part deals with the *cell-free enzyme expression and activity screening results*.

2 Introduction - microfluidics

One of the aims of the OXIPRO project is to develop a novel approach to rapidly select enzyme variants from large libraries. The production of these enzymes is normally in small amounts. Laboratory methods may require high amounts of enzymes and substrates, bulky and expensive instrumentation, labour-intensive sample preparation, and expert operators and personnel. Moreover, enzymes often suffer from low stability, which may be a challenge for solution-based reactions that require long incubation times. Lab-on-a-Chip technology integrates microfluidic and biosensing technologies in miniaturized detection systems. Enzymes immobilized in such microfluidic biosensors benefit from fast reaction rates, high storage stability, suppressed autolysis and ease of use. These systems also overcome traditional biocatalysis monitoring technologies in a lower energy consumption, rapid heat exchange, fast mass transfer, high efficiency, and superior repeatability.

In this Deliverable report (D3.1), the efforts on developing a microfluidic screening platform are reported that includes the design, particle selection, manufacturing optimization and screening of OXIPRO-relevant enzyme activities. The screening platform model was based on packed-bed microfluidics using the horseradish peroxidase (HRP) EC 1.11.1.7 as accessory enzyme that is required for the development of a final colorimetric product and a commercially available laccase EC 1.10.3.2 as test enzymes. Later, the system will be tested on OXIPRO-developed enzymes. Small amounts of enzymes were immobilized by covalent binding on microparticles with a high surface/volume ratio (microfluidic bioreactor). The particles were trapped on a multichannel bioreactor that was developed using 3D printing techniques (high-resolution SLA). The functionality of the system was measured inside the 3D microfluidic layout by monitoring a change in colour due to the catalysed oxidation of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB-assay) by HRP and 2,2'-azinobis[3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid] (ABTS-assay) by the laccase.

3 Screening systems ready for enzyme tests

3.1 Microfluidic screening platform to monitor enzymatic activity

To achieve a functional microfluidic reactor, the first step was to find the most appropriate enzyme immobilization protocol, with the aim to fix them on the surface of the microfluidic platform. The second part was dedicated to the design, manufacturing, and characterization of the microfluidic bioreactor.

3.1.1 Enzymes immobilization in microfluidic platform

The amount and the activity of the enzyme immobilized in a microfluidic chip greatly impact the biocatalytic rate. This can be optimized by adjusting the surface area-to-volume ratio (SAVR) of the microchannel and the diffusion pressure of the solution passing through it. There are 3 main types of structures that can be considered: wall-coated, packed-bed, and monolithic. Herein, LEITAT selected the pack-bed option to have higher probability of substrate capture and subsequent conversion to product than the wall-coated approach, especially when operated at relatively high flow rates [13]. Also, a packed-bed approach enables shorter diffusion distances due to higher surface-to-volume ratios and biocatalyst densities [14]. The main disadvantage regarding the packed-bed approach is the high pressure drop (total pressure in the microfluidic system), especially when the particles are about tens microns in diameter. By using relatively large particles, such pressure issue should not be a problem. In section 3.2.2, the pressure drop was investigated. In the market exist many different particles for enzyme immobilization, however majority of them are agarose-based particles that are not rigid and generates high pressure in the microfluidic system. To avoid a high pressure drop, only two different types of commercially available large particles exists and were selected in the microfluidic reactor (Figure 1):

- 1) silica gel particles with 40-75 μm of diameter with pore size 11 nm from SUPELCO, for immobilization of enzyme on the external surface of the particle;
- 2) methacrylic polymer matrix with 100-300 μm with two different pore sizes 10-20 and 40-60 nm from RESINDION, for immobilization of enzyme on the external and internal surface of the particle.

Figure 1. Microparticles a) silica gel particles (SUPELCO) b) methacrylic polymer matrix (RESINDION)

Next, the immobilization strategy was considered. To assure reusability, different types of immobilizations were considered such as based on ionic binding, His-tag binding, encapsulation, covalent coupling, and crosslinking. Covalent bonds provide the strongest linkage and was chosen as the most suitable immobilization strategy to reduce enzyme leaching caused by shear stress due to the small dimensions of microfluidics devices. However, some enzymes lose their activity during the immobilization process. Therefore, different functional groups were considered. The enzymes were immobilized by covalent binding using two strategies: epoxy-activated support (methacrylic polymer) and ethylamine groups (silica and methacrylic polymer). In Table 1 the conditions and the tested reactive groups are described.

Table 1. Functional groups of the particles selected

Functionality	Supplier	Conditions	Binding	Enzyme reactive groups
 Epoxy	RESINDION	High concentration carbonate buffer, pH 9	Covalent	-SH -NHR -NH ₂ -OH
 Ethylamino	RESINDION, SUPELCO	Glutaraldehyde	Covalent	Primary amines -NH ₂

The gold standard to measure enzymatic activity is by a colorimetric reaction using optical assessment. It is easy to apply in a multi-well plate format, allowing to validate 96 enzymatic assays at the same time. Electrochemical techniques can have higher sensitivity. However, the need to include an electrode array within the screening platform makes the manufacturing process less sustainable. Moreover, main users are not familiar with this technology and often do not have access to this equipment. On the contrary, many laboratories are equipped with spectrophotometry. For this reason, we have chosen optical biosensing using a colorimetric reaction. This should be feasible with the oxidative enzymes targeted in the OXIPRO project.

3.1.1.1 HRP immobilization and activity testing

Oxidase activity is often measured via indirect colorimetric analysis. A universal method is based on a cascade reaction where the oxidase-catalysed substrate oxidation first generates hydrogen peroxide, and secondly, in combination with an HRP-catalysed TMB oxidation, provides a colorimetric product (Figure 2). As exemplified in Figure 2, HRP is present in the cascade reaction with glucose oxidase, catalysing the oxidation of various chromogenic substrates using hydrogen peroxide. For that reason, HRP was selected as a model for a rapid colorimetric quantification of the microfluidic bioreactor. It will allow screening for any oxidase activity.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of GOx/HRP cascade

For the first tests, HRP was immobilized to the amino-functionalized groups of 40-75 μm silica gel particles following a reported protocol [15], where particles were activated in 2.5% glutaraldehyde solution for 3 hours, washed, and incubated with enzyme for 24 hours, enzyme loading 10 mg/g of particles. The activity was evaluated by adding a TMB and H₂O₂ reaction mixture (3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) Liquid Substrate System for ELISA, Sigma-Aldrich). As can be seen in Figure 3, the particles show enzymatic activity as assessed by the immediately blue colour development. These particles were used for optimization of microfluidic bioreactor (size, distance, packaging level, back pressure etc.) (see section 3.2). No particles immobilization yield was measured since it is not an objective for bioreactor optimization.

Figure 3. a) enzyme immobilization reaction on silica gel particles; b) enzymatic activity before adding the substrate and after

3.1.1.2 Laccase immobilization and activity testing

Laccase is a copper-containing oxidase that utilizes molecular oxygen as oxidant and oxidizes phenolic rings to phenoxy radicals. Thereby, laccase activity can be measured directly without the need of enzymatic cascades (see Figure 3). The same silica particles mentioned above and the same protocol for enzyme immobilisation were used. However, no activity was observed after this procedure, no colour change was obtained.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of oxidation of ABTS by laccase

Therefore, functionalization of particles with epoxy groups on a methacrylic polymer matrix 100 - 300 μm and two different pore size were used (10-20 nm and 40-60 nm). The laccase immobilization protocol in a high concentration of carbonate buffer was chosen [16]. Briefly, a concentration of 0.75 M of carbonate buffer (pH 9.0), and an immobilization time around 24 hours were used, enzyme loading 100 mg/g of particles. Laccase activity was measured colorimetrically (420 nm absorbance) by using 0.2 mM ABTS as substrate. In the particles with 10-20 nm pores, low laccase activity was observed. It is important to mention that the particles are not transparent thus it is impossible to demonstrate the low laccase activity (Figure 5 orange curve) because of high absorbance of particles in 420 nm (Figure 5 blue curve), and only by naked eye you can check the colour change by the time. Therefore, the packing bed and detection zone of the bioreactor (see section 3.2) were separated so the enzymatic activity can be calculated. These results will be shown in deliverable Validation of the enzyme biotechnology platform (D3.4.) For the particles with 40-60 nm of pore size, higher activity was observed. However, leaching of enzyme after several washings was observed by assessing the supernatant solutions for enzymatic activity.

Figure 5. Enzymatic activity of immobilized laccase

3.1.1.3 Enzymatic activity

Functionalization of methacrylic polymer matrix 100-300 μm particles with an amino-functionalized group and two different pore sizes were also investigated. Following the protocol mentioned before Sahareet al.[15], the laccase (loading 20 mg/g of particles) and the HRP (loading 10 mg/g of particles) were successfully immobilized. As can be seen in Figure 6 the particles show high enzymatic activity for both enzymes. For laccase-treated particles (Figure 6a), immobilized laccase in high pore size particles (orange line) show an even higher activity than the free enzyme (the same amount of enzyme that was used for immobilization) (yellow line), because the saturation was reached already after 150 seconds compared to free laccase, which in 227 seconds still did not reach saturation. However, the particles with the small pore size showed less activity than those with bigger pore size, probably because of the smaller diffusion through the pores of silica gel particles. For HRP (Figure 6b), immobilized enzyme in high and small pore size particles (red and grey lines) showed the same activity and saturation after 150s. The graph of free HRP is not presented because of the high activity and signal saturation before measurement.

Figure 6. a) enzymatic activity of immobilized laccase; b) enzymatic activity of immobilized HRP

In OXIPRO, Task 3.3 Enzyme immobilisation methodologies includes investigations of enzyme encapsulation in nanocages (encapsulins) or microcapsules. These new immobilization approaches will be considered during the validation of the screening platform at a later stage of the project (Deliverable D3.4).

3.2 Microfluidic bioreactor design and characterisation tests

As previously stated, the screening process uses a microfluidic device that is based on the entrapment of the enzyme-functionalised microparticles. As it was mentioned in 3.1.1.1, small silica particles 40-75 μm shows enzymatic activity and it was used for bioreactor design. According to literature and

experimental parts described in 3.1, it is complicated to have a standard particle size and functionalization group for different type of enzymes. Therefore, we design bioreactor using the small particles in order to determine threshold values for several parameters that was measure therein. By increasing the size of the particles only small changes (Inlet canal dimension) would be needed to the final bioreactor design.

The microfluidic bioreactor was designed with a straight channel with an inlet and an outlet – with a connector for the corresponding tubing, as it is pumped-assisted – and three differentiated parts: the one located closest to the inlet (H1), the one located closest to the outlet (H3) and a middle region in between (H2). The working principle of this device was based on the depth difference between these three segments. The H2 middle region is the point where microparticle entrapment takes place. The channel was sealed with a transparent adhesive layer which, in combination with a low depth in that middle area ($H2 \ll H1, H3$), stopped microparticles and prevented them from passing through the free space between the adhesive and the bottom of the channel (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Bioreactor packing system principle

3.2.1 Best packing dimensions determination

To determine the best particle-packing dimensions, a 7-channel microfluidic device was designed, in which each of the channels had different depths in H1 and H2, as shown in Figure 8a. While H1 has an impact on the amount of microparticles that can be packed in each channel, the entrapment itself depends on H2 – if it is smaller than the size of particles they will not pass through.

Figure 8. a) Channel dimensions of microfluidic bioreactor, b) 3D printed bioreactor

The bioreactor was 3D printed with clear resin for better visibility by means of high resolution stereolithography (SLA), which allows to fabricate complex designs in a wide range of different materials in a short period of time (Figure 6b). Owing to the 3D printer resolution, the minimum H2 channel size was restricted to 25 μm.

The chosen setup for this test is shown in Figure 9. An external pressure source was connected to a multichannel vacuum and pressure microfluidic flow controller that pumped the sample contained in a pressurised reservoir into the microfluidic bioreactor. The 40-75 μm size microparticles were first injected manually with a micropipette, then flow rate was regulated by means of a flow controller. After repeating the same test for all 7 channels they were inspected by optical microscopy (4X lens) to assess the optimal particle packing.

Figure 9. Setup to determine best packing dimensions

It can be seen in Figure 10 that channel 2 presents a good particle packing followed by channel 1 owing to the lowest H2 depth of 25 μm . On the contrary, the channels presenting the worst particle entrapment, with many particles passing through, turned out to be channels 7 and 6 due to the deepest packing area (H2=75 μm). Furthermore, the effect of different channel depths could also be observed by brightness/darkness analysis of the images in Figure 10: channels 1, 3 and 6 were the brightest and presented the lowest density of particles (H1=150 μm), followed by medium brightness/darkness in channels 2, 4 and 7 (H2=250 μm), and ultimately channel 5 displayed the darkest images and highest density (H2=500 μm).

Figure 10. Optical microscope images of the 7 channels with microparticles

Based on the results, it was concluded that channel 2 presented the best packing and thus, its specific H1 and H2 dimensions of 250 μm and 25 μm , respectively, are optimal for microparticle entrapment.

3.2.2 Backpressure determination

Since particles were packed inside of the channel, generating a resistance to the flow, the backpressure caused by the particles and, therefore, the necessary pressure to generate a flow through the channel was determined. The microfluidic device was modified, and all channels adopted channel 2 dimensions (H1=250 μm and H2=25 μm) from this point forward. For this second test, as shown in Figure11, the setup remained unchanged except for a flow rate sensor connected between the sample and the microfluidic device.

Figure 11. Setup for backpressure assay

The followed process was the same as in the previous test. The 40-75 μm size microparticles were first packed inside the channel with a pipette and then the bioreactor was connected to the circuit. The pressure was gradually increased, and then the flow rate was measured with the flow rate sensor, giving an idea of the pressure needed to generate a flow through the microparticles. Figure 12 shows that pressure detected in the pressure control device ranged 0-250 mbar with microparticles and 0-115 mbar without microparticles. In the channel containing microparticles, the pressure was greater than that of the channel without microparticles, showing that they generated a resistance to the flow.

Figure 12. Backpressure generated by microparticles (μP)

With these conditions, the factor accounting for the relation of backpressure between both scenarios, f_p , was defined: computed as the ratio of the slope of the line of backpressure without microparticles and that with microparticles. This factor was found to be 0.45, which means that the pressure needed without microparticles is about half of the pressure required with microparticles. These results show that the required pressure was in the range of millibars, and the device could be operated even by hand without any pumps and valves.

3.2.3 Assays at different flow rate and different number of particles.

To further validate and characterise the bioreactor, flow injection analysis (FIA) with TMB and with HRP-functionalised 40-75 μm microparticles (as specified in section 3.1.1.1.) in the bioreactor chamber were conducted. First, different flow rates were assessed, and afterwards with different amount of microparticles were investigated.

The setup was the same for both assays (Figure 13). The injection valve has two positions, allowing to introduce into the system a small and known volume of sample when shifting from one valve to the other.

Figure 13. Setup for colorimetric assay

The functionalised microparticles were packed inside the bioreactor with a pipette as in previous assays. Then, by means of the injection valve, 32 microliters of TMB were introduced into the system, leading to a colorimetric reaction that produced a product of blue color. This process was recorded with a camera to capture the colour intensity of the product and the video was finally processed with ImageG to extract the intensity values. This assay was repeated for different flow rates and plotted in Figure 14. According to the results, the colour intensity was higher at decreasing flow rates. This behaviour can be explained by the fact that high flow rates do not provide sufficient time for the reaction to occur, thus less amount of product is produced. For instance, a flow rate of 190 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ requires about 50 seconds for the enzymatic reaction to be completed whereas over 400 seconds are needed for an 8 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate. Considering both the reaction time and colour intensity it was concluded that the optimal flow rate was 68 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, as it resulted in a sufficient color intensity signal, and was faster than other flow rates offering similar colour intensities.

Figure 14. Colour intensity at different flow rates. (A.U. stands for Arbitrary Units)

Once the optimal flow rate was estimated, the amount of microparticles was investigated. The flow rate was kept constant at 68 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ thanks to the feedback loop mode of the flow rate sensor, adjusting the pressure to obtain the desired flow rate. Five different quantities of microparticles, from 3000 to 35000, were packed in five different channels and the same process of previous assay was repeated. The results for this assay are shown in Figure 15. The microparticles were packed by volume, e.g., 10 μL of a solution of deionised water with microparticles. The number of particles in a specific volume was computed based on the space occupied by the microparticles and the dimensions of both the channel and the microparticles – assuming they all were the same size and sphere-shaped. As microparticles volume is considerably smaller than that of the volume they occupy inside the channel, the Close Packing of Equal Spheres expression was used:

$$N = 0.74 \times \frac{V_c}{V_s}$$

where 0.74 is a geometrical factor that accounts for the interstitial voids in between microparticles, V_c is the channel volume occupied by the microparticles and V_s is the volume of an individual microparticle.

Figure 15. Colour intensity at different number of microparticles. (A.U. stands for Arbitrary Units)

It was observed that from 1200 to 35000 microparticles both colour intensity and duration did not significantly vary, ranging between 175-215 A.U. and 150 seconds. It was concluded that the optimal number of microparticles is around 12000 as duration of reaction and colour intensity are satisfactory and a smaller amount of microparticles is used in comparison to other quantities giving similar intensities and duration times. The enzymatic load of HRP derivatives that was used is specified in section 3.1.1.1 above. The optimisation of residence time to obtain maximum reaction could vary with different enzymes and different immobilisation strategies.

4 Conclusions - microfluidics

For the Deliverable 3.1, LEITAT has been working on the design, development, and characterization of a novel microfluidic screening platform. The microfluidic platform uses a packed-bed configuration to enable higher surface-to-volume ratios and biocatalyst densities with the minimum enzyme amount. For biofunctionalization of the particles, it was concluded that:

- Laccase and glucose oxidase were selected as model enzymes to represent oxidative enzymes for bioreactor development.
- The well-known colorimetric methods of ABTS and HRP-assisted TMB cascade were identified as suitable assay to monitor and assess enzyme activities of oxidase model enzymes
- Enzymes immobilized on methacrylic polymer matrix 100-300 μm using ethylamine functional group with high pore size 40-60 nm showed the best activity for both laccase and HRP.
- Immobilization on silica gel particles 40-75 μm using amine groups with pore size of 11 nm shows good activity for HRP. However, no activity was detected for the tested laccase.

Different reactor designs were studied for the microfluidic bioreactor. Considering the application and the characteristics given previously, it was concluded that:

- The enzyme-functionalized microparticles generated a resistance to the flow and the backpressure was almost twofold that without microparticles. As pressure values are in the range of millibars, the microfluidic bioreactor can be used by hand without pumps and valves, and allows a simplified set up in labs that will be using this system.
- Channel dimensions of H1=250 μm , H2=25 μm and H3=500 μm provided optimal microparticle packing in the bioreactor design.
- The optimal flow rate and number of particles were found to be 68 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and about 12000, respectively, to achieve a sufficient colour intensity signal over a short period of time.

With these configurations, the microfluidics platform is ready to use for enzyme screening. Up to 10 multiplexed bioreactors are developed using 3D printing techniques (high-resolution SLA) and are available for screening with the partner's established oxidases and laccases. The results will be presented in D3.4.

5 Introduction – cell-free expression & screening

OXIPRO focuses on finding industrial applicable oxidoreductases. To streamline the discovery of such enzymes, we aimed at developing a cell-free expression pipeline for faster enzyme discovery and screening, eliminating steps such as transformation and growth of cells that are typically time-consuming and prone to experimental variation or even failure. In view of the targeted biocatalysts for OXIPRO, we first focused on developing such a pipeline using flavoprotein oxidases as model enzymes. The general scheme for the envisaged protocol is shown below.

Figure 14: Summary of the developed cell-free expression pipeline for the discovery of new flavoproteins.

Flavoprotein oxidases catalyze a wide range of oxidation reactions with high selectivity by using molecular oxygen as electron donor [1]. This makes them of interest for different industries. For example, they can be used to transform low value chemicals into economical viable products, such as the conversion of glycerol to glyceric acid that can be utilized as a dyeing and tanning agent in textiles, as a flavoring agent and preservative in food and beverage, as an anti-aging ingredient in cosmetics, or in plastics and adhesives [2,3]. Other applications include the use of these oxidases as biosensors or as biocatalysts for the production of hydrogen peroxide. Although some flavoprotein oxidases are produced and applied for decades many are still lack proper characteristics for their desired industrial purpose [1]. Analysis of genome sequences and literature data reveals that nature harbors many unexplored flavoprotein oxidases [4]. This begs for the development of a quick and easy tool to discover and characterize these enzymes. An ideal candidate approach for this is cell-free expression

as it removes time-consuming constraints of working with cells and allows for rapid expression by omitting cloning, expression and purification steps [5].

Available cell-free expression formats based on *Escherichia coli* comes in two forms. The first one is the PURExpress® system by New England Biolabs in which the necessary proteins for translation and transcription are purified from *E. coli* and mixed in a one-pot system. This is often used for the incorporation of unnatural amino acids into proteins [6]. The second option is the NEBExpress® system by New England Biolabs. This system is based on *E. coli* cell-free lysate and is reported to have higher expression levels than the PURExpress® system [7]. Beside cell lysate, the cell-free expression mix also requires a RNA polymerase, often in the form of T7 RNA polymerase, an energy mixture, and all the canonical amino acids [7]. By coupling cell-free expression to a suitable oxidase activity assay a quick discovery tool has been developed for the OXIPRO consortium for flavoprotein oxidases discovery.

6 Results

6.1 Cell-free expression of a flavoprotein oxidase

Although the production of in-house cell-free expression mixture is advancing, it remains challenging and time consuming to implement the reported protocols [7-10]. For this reason, it was decided to use a commercially available cell-free expression kit. Since the goal in OXIPRO is to use cell-free expression as a screening system, a lysate-based strategy for cell-free expression was found to be adequate, and the NEBExpress® Cell-free *E. coli* Protein Synthesis System was chosen based on the relatively low price per reaction (~€12 per 50 µL). As model flavoprotein oxidase, hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase (HMFO) was chosen due to its high expression in *E. coli*, available HPLC analysis protocols for monitoring the reaction, and the availability of a colorimetric read-out from vanillyl alcohol conversion to vanillin [11]. The HMFO-encoding gene was cloned into a pET28 vector using the Golden Gate assembly methodology [12]. Then, 250 ng of plasmid was added to the NEBExpress® Cell-free *E. coli* Protein Synthesis System mixture and mixed according to the protocol provided. To confirm the expression of HMFO, the resulting mixture was analyzed by SDS-PAGE. The gel analysis indicated expression of a protein corresponding to the expected mass of HMFO. To confirm the expression, two substrate conversion tests were performed. The first was with the substrate hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) which showed the formation of the expected products, FDCA, FFCA and DFF, upon HPLC analysis [11]. The second test was with vanillyl alcohol as substrate, where the formation of vanillin by the expressed HMFO was confirmed by absorption at 340 nm. To conclude, the cell-free expression of HMFO using the NEBExpress® system was confirmed using both assessment strategies.

Figure 15: HMFO cell-free expression

a) Coomassie stained 12% SDS-PA gel with 15 µL of sample loaded. - is cell-free mixture without plasmid; + is positive control; 'hmfo' is cell-free HMFO expression and 'pure' is previously purified HMFO b) Absorbance spectra of cell-free expressed HMFO with 1 mM of vanillyl alcohol (blue) and cell-free mixture without plasmid with 1 mM of vanillyl alcohol (black). Both spectra are taken after 2 hours incubation at 24 °C. c) HPLC chromatograms after 20 hours incubation of cell-free HMFO expression mixture with 1 mM HMF.

Next, a few optimization steps were tried, as shown in Figure 3. The addition of the flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) cofactor or different incubation times did not appear to improve the cell-free expression of HMFO. The optimal condition for the expression of HMFO was at 37 °C, 800 rpm for 4 hours without the addition of extra FAD cofactor.

Figure 16: Optimization of HMFO cell-free expression

Coomassie stained 12% SDS-PAGE gel with 15 μ L of sample loaded. M are marker proteins and the arrow points at the expected band of \sim 70 kDa a) the amounts of μ M show the amount of FAD that was added to the cell-free expression mixture of HMFO. b) Neg is cell-free mixture incubated for 4 hours without any plasmid. The others show the amounts of hours a cell-free mixture was incubated at 37 $^{\circ}$ C while expressing HMFO.

According to literature the cell-free expression system should be able to express linear DNA containing a T7 promoter, a ribosome binding site and a T7 terminator [7]. This would save OXIPRO partners valuable time as they can in theory express ordered genes without extra cloning steps. Linear DNA containing the described parts and the HMFO gene was obtained by PCR cloning and 250 ng was added to the NEBExpress[®] System mixture and ran with the determined optimal condition for HMFO expression. The SDS-PAGE analysis indicates that HMFO is still expressed. However, the expression appeared significantly lower and thus it was decided to continue with plasmids instead of linear DNA fragments.

Figure 17: Cell-free expression of linear DNA

Coomassie stained 12% PA gel with 15 μ L of sample. M shows the marker proteins; Neg is cell-free expression without plasmid; Linear shows cell-free expression mixture which expressed HMFO using only a linear piece of DNA with a T7 promoter, ribosome binding site and the HMFO gene.

To confirm that the cell-free expression mixture works with more flavoprotein oxidases than just HMFO a range of different oxidases were cloned into a pET28 vector and expressed in the cell-free mixture. The resulting gel can be seen in Figure 18. Some enzymes show a clear band on the gel and are presumably expressed. However, not all the enzymes were expressed. It appears that enzymes that are difficult to express in *E. coli* are also difficult to express with the cell-free expression system. This, however, still needs to be confirmed with a larger set of enzyme candidates.

Figure 18: Cell-free expression of a range of different oxidases

Coomassie stained 12% SDS with 15 μ L of sample loaded of different flavoprotein oxidases. The little red dots indicate the expected mass. A red cross above the lane indicates no observed expression or overexpressed band in the gel.

6.2 Oxidase assays coupled with cell-free expression mixture

Although it can be used with any enzyme in question, SDS-PAGE analysis does not always provide clear proof of expression and will not reveal whether an enzyme is expressed in a functional form. Therefore, an activity assay needs to be coupled with the cell-free expression system to create a pipeline for a quick and easy flavoenzyme discovery protocol. Preferably this assay should be adapted to a 96-well plate format to facilitate assessment of multiple enzyme targets or varying conditions. Upon searching literature, two generic assaying methods were identified; the use of a sensor that monitor oxygen, and

the use of enzymatic assays that monitor the development of a chromogenic product. OxoPlates® are round bottom 96-well multiplate with an oxygen sensor integrated on the bottom of each well. Plates were kindly provided by Presens. These were first tested with purified N-acetyl-glucosamine oxidase as model enzyme to see if they are capable of measuring oxygen consumption. As can be seen in Figure 19a, the OxoPlate® is capable of measuring the oxygen consumption upon the oxidation of glucose by the oxidase. Next, a cell-free expression mixture with and without HMFO-expressing plasmid were tested with the OxoPlate®, resulting in Figure 19b. As is shown in the figure the oxygen consumption can be monitored by the expressed HMFO, thus showing the suitability of the OxoPlate in this pipeline. However, the negative controls also seemed to give oxygen consumption. The apparent background activity lowered the reliability of this method. For this reason and the relatively high cost (€12.50 per plate) of an Oxoplate compared to a regular chromogenic assay it was decided to step away from this strategy.

Figure 19: Oxoplate coupled with cell-free expression

- a) Oxoplate results of oxidation of glucose by N-acetyl-glucosamine oxidase.
 b) cell-free mixture coupled with an Oxoplate assay.

HRP-based oxidase assays are based on the production of hydrogen peroxide produced by the flavoprotein oxidases. This hydrogen peroxide is used by HRP to perform a coupled reaction to produce a distinctive absorption. Multiple HRP assays were tried with the cell-free expression mixture but most, e.g., Amplex Red, gave background signals and were thus not compatible. The HRP/DCHBS/AAP assay however worked. Moreover, the reaction can be followed with the naked eye. Because of the low cost and ease of use, this assay was chosen to be coupled to the cell-free expression workflow.

6.3 Pipeline usage for flavoprotein oxidase discovery

As proof of principle; homologs of alditol oxidases were used to validate the cell-free expression pipeline. Using genome mining three potential candidates were identified and their genes were

ordered from Twist Biosciences. The genes were cloned into a pET28 GG SUMO vector using the Golden Gate assembly methodology [12] and were expressed with the NEBExpress® System. To verify their activity, the HRP/DCHBS/AAP assay was combined with the cell-free expression mixture. Product formation was monitored in a plate reader at an absorption of 515 nm, as shown in Figure 20b.

The developed cell-free expression pipeline confirmed that all three homologues are active against glycerol. This result was obtained within 48 hours of the arrival of the synthetic genes. This proves the effectiveness of the cell-free expression pipeline developed for the OXIPRO consortium.

Figure 20: cell-free expression pipeline with three new alditol oxidases

a) Photo taken of the wells after the cell-free expression & assay pipeline. Neg is with none expressed cell-free mixture the others are with expressed cell-free mixture with the named enzyme. b) HRP assay results measured at 515 nm with a plate reader (Biotech). c) 12% SDS gel showing the expression of the new alditol oxidases. Red arrow indicates the expected bands.

7 Conclusions - cell-free expression & screening

The goal of OXIPRO was to establish a working pipeline for enzyme screening using cell-free expression. In this first phase of the project, RUG worked on developing new methodology for this. By using HMFO as a model oxidase it was shown that commercially available kits are capable of expressing an active flavoprotein oxidase. It was also demonstrated that enzymatic assays with easy read-out can be combined with the cell-free expression. As a proof of concept, by coupling the cell-free expression system with a suitable chromogenic assay, three new alditol oxidases were shown to be functionally expressed within 48 hours of the arrival of synthetic genes to the lab, thus, proving the effectiveness of the cell-free expression pipeline. With traditional methods for cloning and expressing (and often requiring purification) the assessment of new gene products may take up to a week of work. Current limitations for the developed cell-free expression pipeline is the high cost of the cell-free mixture.

However, this may be solved by making the cell-free mixture in house instead of buying it commercially.

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